

Gastroesophageal Reflux Disease

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ABSTRACT

Gastroesophageal reflux disease is one of the most common gastric problem in middle age group as well as in old age group. It is characterized by decreased LES tone leading to reflux of acidic contents and food items from stomach into the esophagus particularly when the patients lies down or on bending and straining. It causes epigastric burning, retrosternal chest pain, nausea, vomiting and in long standing cases cough, asthma and recurrent chest infections.

It is diagnosed clinically but in case of diagnostic uncertainty Lower esophageal ph monitoring is done. Proton pump inhibitors and life style modifications are mainstay of treatment. In advanced and resistant cases however, anti-reflux surgery is done. In untreated and longstanding GERD, barretts esophagus is a serious complication. It is replacement of cuboidal epithelium of LES and lower esophagus by the columnar epithelium. Although it can be asymptomatic it can predispose to malignancy in long run.

Key words: GERD, reflux, barretts esophagus,

Introduction:

Gastro-esophageal reflux disease affects nearly 30 percent of the population worldwide. It is common in health individuals too and is defined as reflux of stomach contents into the esophagus. In healthy individuals reflux is followed by peristaltic wave which clears the gullet followed by alkaline saliva which neutralizes the stomach acid relieving one from the symptoms and signs of reflux.

Prolonged exposure of lower esophageal mucosa to gastric contents leads to esophagitis. There are numerous factors leading to the development of GERD which include defective esophageal clearance, Obesity, Hiatus hernia, Lower esophageal dystony , delayed gastric emptying and increased intra-abdominal pressure. The LES is normally contracted and it relaxes only during swallowing. Some patients with GERD have reduced LES tone permitting reflux in response to increased intra-abdominal pressure.

Pressure gradient between abdominal and thoracic cavity which normally pinches the hiatus is lost reflux. However, hiatus hernia can be

asymptomatic too. Pregnancy and obesity leading to increased intra-abdominal pressure are common predisposing factors leading to reflux. Dietary fat, alcohol, chocolate and coffee relax the LES and thus exaggerate the symptoms.

Clinical Features:

The most important clinical features of GERD are heartburn and regurgitation often provoked by bending, straining and lying down. As the reflux acid irritates the larynx this may cause choking. Other less common features include atypical chest pain mimicking angina, chronic cough, asthma and recurrent chest infections.

Some of the extra-esophageal manifestation of GERD includes feeling of globus sensation, feeling of lump in the throat. Repeated exposure of pharynx to the acid leads to increased tonicity of Upper esophageal sphincter. Acid reflux leads to bronchospasm leading to development of asthma like symptoms.

Alarm symptoms for GERD include dysphagia , Odynophagia , bleeding, anemia and weight loss. There is clear cut but overlapping between GERD and dyspepsia. Dyspepsia is defined as only epigastric discomfort without acid reflux or regurgitation, present for more than a month.

Complications:

Long standing GERD is associated with wide range of complications.

Inflammation of esophagus, esophagitis is one of the most common complication presents as persistent retrosternal burning and on endoscopy there is mild redness and/or severe bleeding or ulceration. This can also lead to anemia and its symptoms.

Long standing acid reflux from stomach to lower end of esophagus leads to changing in the squamous lining of lower esophagus to columnar known as Columnar lined esophagus and/or Barrets esophagus. Barrets esophagus itself doesn't present with any symptoms but it can be a predisposing factor for esophageal carcinoma. There is 20-30 fold increase in the relative risk of esophageal carcinoma however absolute risk remains 0.1-0.5

percent per year. Multiple systematic biopsies are required to diagnose this condition. There are different treatment modalities for it based.

Columnar lined esophagus with dysplasia is treated with radiofrequency ablation and photodynamic therapy. If there is Barrett's esophagus without dysplasia then repeated interval endoscopy (3-5 yearly) until any change is observed. In case of high grade dysplasia, esophagectomy with RFA is the procedure of choice.

Long standing esophagitis can lead to benign esophageal stricture which presents classically as dysphagia more to solids than liquids. It is diagnosed by upper GI endoscopy with biopsy to rule out malignancy and treated by endoscopic balloon dilatation.

Diagnosis:

Young patients who present with mild symptoms need to be investigated for GERD and must be treated empirically. However, those patients presenting at age 50-55 years with alarm symptoms need further investigations. Endoscopy is the investigation of choice. If there is diagnostic uncertainty then 24 hour Ph monitoring is the investigation of choice, particularly if surgical options are under consideration. If ph is less than 4 for 6-7 percent of the study time then it confirms

the diagnosis of GERD. Impedance testing can detect weekly acidic or alkaline reflux if it goes undetected by standard ph monitoring.

Management:

Life style advices for patients of GERD include weight loss, avoiding foods which worsen these symptoms. The patients who experience nocturnal symptoms are advised to elevate the head end to avoid reflux and to stop taking late night meals. GERD has been found to have high prevalence in patients who are chronic smokers.

Once these life style modifications are not helpful then long term treatment with Proton pump inhibitors is advised. Some patients may need life long treatment at lowest acceptable dose as stopping treatment may cause recurrence of symptoms. In case of esophageal dysmotility, domperidone is advised to help. In patients who require PPIs for more than one year. H.Pylori eradication is recommended. In patients who take long term PPI, reduced absorption of iron, B12 and magnesium is noted. PPIs can also predispose to enteric infections such as salmonella, campylobacter and clostridium difficile.

In patients who do not respond to medical treatment then laproscopic antireflux surgery is advised.

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